

EELISA

European University

EELISA INNOCORE

Deliverable D5.2 EELISA's portfolio of Clusters

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EELISA InnoCORE Partners

Number	Role	Name in original language	Name in English	Short name	Country
1	COO	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	Technical University of Madrid	UPM	Spain
2	BEN	École Nationale des Ponts et Chaussées	National School of Civil Engineering	ENPC	France
3	BEN	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	Friedrich-Alexander University Erlangen-Nürnberg	FAU	Germany
4	BEN	İstanbul Teknik Üniversitesi	Istanbul Technical University	ITU	Turkey
5	BEN	Scuola Normale Superiore	Higher Normal School	SNS	Italy
6	BEN	Scuola Superiore di Studi Universitari e di Perfezionamento Sant'Anna	Sant'Anna School of Advanced Studies	SSSA	Italy
7	BEN	Universitatea Politehnica din Bucuresti	Politehnica University of Bucharest	UPB	Romania
8	BEN	Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem	Budapest University of Technology and Economics	BME	Hungary
9	BEN	Université Paris Sciences et Lettres	Université PSL	PSL	France

Alliance members

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Executive summary

This document is prepared within the work package WP5–‘ Set up initiatives for joint research projects (Enable joint research)’, as deliverable D5.2 ‘EELISA's portfolio of Clusters’ of the project EELISA INNOVation and Common Research strategy (hereinafter referred to as EELISA InnoCORE), co-funded by European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101035811.

The document describes how “Clusters” are included in the EELISA InnoCORE strategy for the research and innovation dimension of the EELISA alliance, it provides the definition of “Clusters” in the context of the EELISA InnoCORE project, it explains the aim and purpose of “Clusters”, it outlines the methodology used so far for identifying “Clusters” and how it will change when the EELISA InnoCORE Platform will be delivered, it includes connections between “Clusters” and [EELISA communities](#), and links between task 5.2 of WP5 and other tasks within WP5 and other WPs of the EELISA Erasmus and EELISA InnoCORE projects, it proposes key performance indicators that allow measuring the success of creating and putting in place clusters.

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Review and quality check by EELISA

In order to guarantee coordination and complementarity and avoid overlapping between the two projects, the following people from EELISA have been consulted for the production of this deliverable: Juan Manuel Muñoz Guijosa and Isabel Salgueiro from UPM.

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Glossary- Abbreviations and definitions

(alphabetic order)

CA. Consortium Agreement. The consortium agreement is a private agreement between the beneficiaries, to set out the rights and obligations amongst themselves. (It does NOT involve the European Commission/Agency.)

Communication. Taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its research outputs to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.

Dissemination. The public disclosure of the research outputs by any appropriate means, including by scientific publications in any medium.

Exploitation. The utilisation of research outputs in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.

EELISA Community. The [EELISA communities](#) are mission-driven working groups that bring together students, teachers, and researchers from all partner universities with prestigious professionals, grassroots organizations, citizens, private companies, and public institutions to find innovative solutions to real-world challenges.

EELISA Cluster. EELISA Clusters are science-based working groups that will work on the scientific and technological solutions that may contribute to solve the societal challenges identified by [EELISA Communities](#).

GA. Grant Agreement. This is the grant contract concluded between the EU and the beneficiaries. It establishes the rights and obligations that govern the grant. It consists of a core text and annexes (for instance, fixing the project content and the project budget).

KER. Key Exploitable Results. We refer to the research outputs with major potential for being exploited within the project.

KPIs. Key Performance Indicators

Project Results/ Project Outputs. By project results we understand a unit of knowledge that has been generated out of a project. This includes any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, prototypes, demonstrators, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected. It is not limited to pioneering discoveries, but may also include new methodologies/processes, adaptations, insights, alternative applications of prior knowledge. Along this document, we use project results and project outputs indistinctively, with the same meaning.

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1 Introduction to EELISA InnoCORE

The European Engineering Learning Innovation and Science Alliance (EELISA) is a bottom-up alliance of European higher education institutions representing more than 180,000 students and 50,000 graduates each year, 16,000 faculty members and 11,000 administrative staff. EELISA is one of the 41 European Universities selected by the European Commission under the Erasmus+ call, focused on education. EELISA was selected during the second pilot call. With the formalization of this European University, partners are initiating an unprecedented level of institutionalised cooperation between our institutions in order to gradually achieve our long-term ambitious vision: the education of European Engineers.

A pillar of EELISA will be the setting-up of [EELISA Communities](#): challenge-based working groups where citizens, private companies and academia will collaborate to face societal challenges. EELISA Communities will be the place where education, research, innovation and public debate coexist and connect, enhancing the connection of engineering with society.

Within this framework, **EELISA InnoCORE is conceived as an integral part of the Alliance**, being a tool supporting, strengthening and delving deeper into the cooperation set up by EELISA. Building on the ecosystem of EELISA Communities, **EELISA InnoCORE focuses on the R&I dimension of the Alliance in a three-step plan**: 1) make our researchers and innovators know each other, create spaces for dialogue with citizens and with non-academic actors and set up a portfolio of shared scientific infrastructures; 2) foster and support the development of joint R&I actions and the creation of new structures (research groups, clusters, joint labs, start-ups, scientific parks) and 3) optimize the outreach of these actions.

EELISA InnoCORE will be running for three years and it is structured around seven (7) work packages (WPs), focusing each on one of the key elements of the project. Under InnoCORE, EELISA partners will work on establishing a portfolio of joint research areas and defining a joint roadmap of research infrastructures (WP2). InnoCORE will map existing research infrastructures and facilities (WP4), with two aims: establishing the rules for opening their use and defining the main features of a booking system so that these resources can be used by all researchers of the Alliance, on the one hand; eventually, establishing a framework for jointly investing in new infrastructures.

EELISA InnoCORE will support the collaboration and the setting-up of joint research projects among the members of the Alliance through the development of a networking platform (WP5), the setting-up of clusters¹, the launching of seed funding for prospective young researchers (WP5) and the use of existing or new equipment and facilities in labs to foster collaborations (WP4). In addition to this, EELISA InnoCORE has two work packages dedicated to interlinking the incubation, start-up and entrepreneurship support services of the members of the alliance (WP7) and to foster the participation of society in science (WP7) and strengthening relations with the industry world (WP6). UPM will coordinate and lead the management of the project, being responsible for guiding the project in cross-cutting issues, such as gender balance (WP1). Lastly, the project has a dedicated work package on open science (WP3).

¹ Science-based working groups that will work on scientific and technological solutions than can help solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities.

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WP	WP title	WP Leader
WP1	Coordination, evaluation, communication and dissemination	UPM
WP2	EELISA Research and Innovation Strategy	ITÜ
WP3	EELISA Strategic Framework for Open Science practices	UPB
WP4	EELISA Multi Labs (sharing facilities & equipment)	PSL
WP5	Set up initiatives for joint research projects (Enable joint research)	SNS
WP6	Reinforcing cooperation in R&I with other sectors, especially academia-business cooperation	BME
WP7	Create the "embedding" for EELISA-wide R&I structures (Optimize outreach)	FAU

Table 1: List of work packages and WP leaders

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2 EELISA's portfolio of Clusters

The EELISA **innoCORE** strategy has a twofold approach to the research and innovation dimension of the EELISA alliance, built on an ecosystem of horizontal and vertical structure

Horizontal approach: Achieved through the **EELISA communities** already created to transform the educational dimension of our alliance. EELISA communities are oriented to face societal challenges that raise scientific and technological needs that must be addressed by researchers and innovators. The EELISA communities are strategic and expected to last several years. EELISA Communities create a space for dialogue between researchers, innovators and society.

Vertical approach: Achieved through the **EELISA clusters**, which are created when some researchers and innovators decide to develop joint actions to meet the scientific and technological needs of EELISA communities. These structures are diverse (in size, ambition and scope) and mainly instrumental. They start by carrying out specific joint actions to address a scientific and technological challenge, and may last for a long time if they decide to continue meeting the needs of others.

Figure 1 Vertical and horizontal approach

Clusters are research and innovation-based working groups addressing the scientific and technological solutions that may contribute to solve the societal challenges identified by EELISA Communities. The main goal of Clusters is to boost the capability of the EELISA network to solve scientific and technological challenges, sharing ideas, methods, labs, funds, manpower.

In order to create **EELISA clusters**, SNS and SSSA, in collaboration with FAU, are developing the EELISA InnoCORE Platform (task 5.1). To define the entries of the EELISA InnoCORE

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Platform, and to design the algorithm that makes the creation of clusters more efficient, we have asked WP5 leaders to collect research projects pertinent to the EELISA mission among the researchers of their Institution. In particular, we asked WP5 leaders to fill in an excel file with research projects labelled as detailed below.

We underline that this first collection of research projects was meant to define the entries of the EELISA InnoCORE Platform, and to design the algorithm that makes the creation of clusters more efficient. A more comprehensive collection of research projects will be achieved by means of the EELISA InnoCORE Platform.

2.1 Collecting research projects

Research projects must contain the following information:

- Personal information of the researcher proposing the research project. It includes compulsory entries (Name, Surname, Institutional affiliation, e-mail address) and facultative entries (statement of research interest, link to personal website and/or to laboratories/infrastructures the researcher works within).
- Research project information. It includes compulsory entries (title of the project, a short (<1000 characters) abstract of the project (without acronyms), the action the researcher is proposing) and facultative entries (any available laboratory/infrastructure that could be useful for the project, any possible already existing EELISA Community that is related to the project).

For what concerns the entry about laboratory/infrastructure, it would be useful to link this entry with the catalogue developed within the WP4 of InnoCORE. For what concerns the entry about EELISA Communities it would be useful to link this entry with the catalogue developed within EELISA.

Proposed actions must be chosen among a predefined set of options. The following possible actions have been proposed so far: Scientific collaboration, Exchange of students, Exchange of staff, Organization of conferences, Organization of workshops, Partnership, Follow-up projects, new projects, PhD thesis, post-doctoral fellowship, Graduate student internships.

For what concerns Graduate student internships, it would be useful to link this entry to the Task 5.8 of the EELISA Erasmus WP5 which aims at coordinating graduate students research internships in an international research laboratory.

- Labels of the project. It includes compulsory entries (Sustainable Development Goals, Strategic Research Areas, Panels, Keywords) and facultative entries (Free Keywords). For what concerns the Sustainable Development Goals related to the project they must be chosen among the predefined 17 SDGs included in the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, adopted by all United Nations Member States in 2015. They can be found here <https://sdgs.un.org/>

Strategic Research Areas related to the project must be chosen among the predefined 11 research areas selected as strategic by the EELISA consortium at the kick-off meeting (definition taken from D2.1):

1. Digital

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2. Climate, Energy & Mobility
3. Social Sciences & Humanities
4. Health
5. Artificial Intelligence
6. Connectivity
7. Food, Bio-economy, Natural Resources, Agriculture & Environment
8. Culture, Creativity & Inclusive Society
9. Smart Industry & Space Technologies
10. Natural Sciences
11. Advanced Materials Science and Engineering

Panels and Keywords refer to the structure of the European Research Council (ERC) that can be found [here](#).

Panels refer to the predefined set of 27 options (SH1, SH2, up to SH6; PE1, PE2, up to PE10; LS1, LS2, up to LS9). Keywords refer to the Predefined set of 399 options in which the Panels are divided (e.g. one example per Panel: SH2_1, SH2_2 up to SH2_11; PE1_1, PE1_2, up to PE1_21; LS4_1, LS4_2 up to LS4_8).

Free Keywords can be arbitrarily chosen by the researcher.

The aforementioned information requested for the research projects are summarized in the Table below.

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ENTRY DESCRIPTION	COMPULSORY (Y/N)	TYPE
PERSONAL INFO (in phase of registration to the platform)		
Proponent (Name, Surname)	Y,Y	free text
Institution e-mail address	Y	free text
e-mail address	Y	free text
Statement of research	N	free text
link to website (both personal and lab websites)	N	free text
RESEARCH PROJECT INFO (avoiding acronyms)		
TITLE	Y	free text
ABSTRACT	Y	free text
ACTION PROPOSED	Y	predefined set of options (at least one option must be selected but it should also be possible to select more than one option) link to EELISA WP5 (task 5.8)
LAB & INFRASTRUCTURES	N	link to EELISA InnoCORE WP4 (LAB & INFRASTRUCTURES catalogue)
COMMUNITIES	N	link to EELISA communities
LABELS (Input for the «matching function»)		
SDG (Sustainable Development Goals)	Y	Predefined set of 17 options (at least one option must be selected but it should also be possible to select more than one option)
SRA (Strategic Research Areas)	Y	Predefined set of 11 options (at least one option must be selected but it should also be possible to select more than one option)
Panel (from the ERC panel structure)	Y	Predefined set of 27 options (PE X) (at least one option must be selected but it should also be possible to select more than one option)
KEYWORDS (from the ERC panel structure)	Y	Predefined set of 399 options (PE X_Y) (at least three options must be selected but it should also be possible to select more than three options)
Free keywords (FREEKs)	N	free text

Table 2 Information requested for the research projects

Titles, SDGs, SRAs, Panels, Keywords, and FREEKs of the research projects collected via the excel file can be found in the file Annex-proto-clusters.pdf.

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2.2 Matching similar/related research projects

To find similar/related research projects we have adopted the following matching function:

- COMMON LABELS

The first simplest option to find a match among different research projects is based on common labels (SDGs, SRAs, Pales, Keywords). Research projects that share one or more labels represent possible matches. The largest is the number of common labels, the higher is the degree of match (e.g. 1 for one common label, 2 for two common labels and so on). The match can be obtained only for research projects proposed by different Institutions.

We provide below some examples of “Proto-clusters” found through this procedure.

2.2.1 PROTO-CLUSTER#1 Technology, Innovation and Natural Sciences for a healthy society

PARTNERS INVOLVED:
FAU, UPB, UPM, SNS, SSSA

COMMON SDGs: 3 Good health and well being

COMMON SRAs: 4 Health

COMMON ERC Panels: LS7 Prevention, Diagnosis and Treatment of Human Diseases

COMMON ERC Keywords: LS7_2 Medical technologies and tools for prevention, diagnosis, monitoring and treatment of diseases; LS7_12 Health care, including care for the aging population; LS7_14 Digital medicine, e-medicine, medical applications of artificial intelligence

A visualization of proto-cluster#1 can be found below.

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Figure 2 Proto-cluster 2

MAIN GOALS:

- To develop tools for monitoring gait disturbances/brain signals by means of wearable inertial sensors.
- To develop artificial tactile sensors.
- To develop artificial intraurethral sphincter for urinary incontinence.
- To allow dissemination experiences for visually impaired people by means of data sonification.
- To develop software systems to assist visually impaired people.

This Proto-Cluster is the result of 6 research projects with the following titles:

FAU1: Development of an artificial intraurethral sphincter for therapy of urinary incontinence

UPB10: Sound of Vision

UPM1: Digitalization to learn Multiple Sclerosis evolution (Long Term Gait Monitoring)

UPM4: Wearable devices for the prevention, diagnosis and treatment of diseases

SNS6: Data Sonification

SSSA1: Sensing Sciences and Technologies

2.2.2 PROTO-CLUSTER#2 Social Sciences for an Inclusive Society

This proto-cluster is linked to the Communities «Open Science» and «ES:O4E» (Egalitarian Societies: Opportunities for Everyone)

PARTNERS INVOLVED: ENPC, ITU, SSSA, UPB

COMMON SDGs: 4. Quality education, 5. Gender equality

COMMON SRAs: 3. Social Sciences & Humanities, 8. Culture, Creativity & Inclusive Society

COMMON ERC Panels: SH3: The Social World and Its Diversity

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COMMON ERC Keywords: SH3_11 Social aspects of teaching and learning, curriculum studies, education and educational policies, SH3_12 Communication and information, networks, media, SH3_13 Digital social research

A visualization of proto-cluster#2 can be found below.

Figure 3 Proto-cluster 3

MAIN GOALS:

- To create a professional figure able to design innovative territorial development plans.
- To embed digital social inclusion in universities by means of an interactive platform.
- To form an international and inter-sectoral network of organizations in EU, Africa & South America working on a joint research program in the field of agroforestry.

This Proto-Cluster is the result of 4 research projects with the following titles:

ENPC3: Narrative CV

ITU15: Digital Social Inclusion

SSSA4: UNDERTREES

UPB5: Skilled: Sustainable Skills for Local Developer

2.2.3 PROTO-CLUSTER#3 Digital Innovation for Reducing Carbon Footprint

PARTNERS INVOLVED: BME, ITU, SNS

COMMON SDGs 11. Sustainable Cities and Communities

COMMON SRAs 2. Climate, Energy and Mobility, 3. Social Sciences and Humanities

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COMMON ERC PANELS SH3. The Social World and Its Diversity, SH7. Human Mobility, Environment, and Space
 COMMON ERC KEYWORDS SH3_14 Social studies of science and technology, SH7_6 Environmental and climate change, societal impact and policy

A visualization of proto-cluster#3 can be found below.

Figure 4 Proto-cluster 3

MAIN GOALS

- To raise social awareness about carbon footprint due to Internet.
- To develop a series of actions to decrease carbon footprint due to mobility.
- To decrease carbon footprint due to high performance computing.

This Proto-Cluster is the result of 5 research projects with the following titles:

BME2: Creation of mobility packages based on user groups

BME5: An extended method for the analysis of workplace mobility planning measures

BME6: Creation of a micro mobility index for cities to support new mobility services

ITU7: Online Footprint – A serious game for reducing digital carbon emission

SNS4: Reducing the environmental impact of High-Performance Computing

2.2.4 PROTO-CLUSTER#4 Computational Chemistry and Spectroscopy for a clean and sustainable environment

PARTNERS INVOLVED: ITU, PSL, SNS

COMMON SDGs 6. Clean water and sanitation, 7. affordable and clean energy,

11. Sustainable cities and communities, 15. Life on Land

COMMON SRAs 2. Climate, Energy & Mobility, 10. Natural Science

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COMMON ERC PANELS PE4: Physical and Analytical Chemical Sciences

COMMON ERC KEYWORDS PE4_2: Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques, PE4_13 Theoretical and computational chemistry

A visualization of proto-cluster#4 can be found below.

Figure 5 Proto-cluster 4

MAIN GOALS

- To develop spectroscopic predictions of atmospheric pollutants and water contaminants by means of computational chemistry.
- To increase the recycling of wastes based on spectroscopic analysis and thermodynamic.

This Proto-Cluster is the result of 4 research projects with the following titles:

ITU10: National Center for HPC (including computational chemistry)

PSL1; Materials recycling, urban mines and secondary resource

SNS2: Rotational and vibrational signatures of atmospheric pollutants

SNS3: Computational prediction of the spectroscopic properties of water contaminants

A complete visualization of the Proto-Clusters identified so far can be found below.

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Figura 6 Proto-cluster 1-4

2.2.5 NOTES ON THE FIRST EELISA PROTO-CLUSTERS

ALL EELISA partners are involved.
 A good fraction of SDGs (3,4,5,6,7,11,15) are involved.
 A good fraction of SRAs (2,3,4,8,10) are involved.
 ALL ERC domains (PE, LS, SH) are involved.

To measure the success of creating and putting in place clusters we identify the following key performance indicators:

1. KPI 1 Research papers produced by authors belonging to different Institutions in the EELISA network;
2. KPI 2 Workshops organised by researchers belonging to different Institutions and included into EELISA Clusters;
3. KPI 3 Joint research proposal to be submitted to the European Research Council to support the EELISA Clusters development.

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INSTITUTION & PROJECT #	TITLE (*)	LINK WITH COMMUNITIES	Sustainable Development Goals (*)	STRATEGIC RESEARCH AREA (*)	PANEL (*)	Keywords (from the ERC panel structure) (*)	FreeKs (Free Keywords) (*)
BME1	Comparison of heuristic optimization methods		11: Sustainable cities and communities	2: Climate, energy and mobility	SH7 Human Mobility, Environment, and Space	SH7_9 transportation, SH7_9 mobility, SH7_7 cities, PE6_7 artificial intelligence, PE6_7 intelligent systems, PE6_6 algorithms and complexity, SH7_10 spatial analysis	heuristic, optimization
BME2	Creation of mobility packages based on user groups		11: Sustainable cities and communities	2: Climate, energy and mobility	SH7 Human Mobility, Environment, and Space	SH7_9 transportation, SH7_9 mobility, SH7_7 cities, SH3_6 group behaviour, SH7_6 climate change, SH7_6 societal impact	MaaS, package
BME3	Development of a method for the interconnection of multimodal transport networks		11: Sustainable cities and communities	2: Climate, energy and mobility	SH7 Human Mobility, Environment, and Space	SH7_9 transportation, SH7_9 mobility, SH7_7 cities, PE6_7 artificial intelligence, PE6_7 intelligent systems, PE6_6 algorithms and complexity, SH7_10 spatial analysis	multimodal, routing

BME4	Activity chain optimization with mass data analysis		11: Sustainable cities and communities	2: Climate, energy and mobility	SH7 Human Mobility, Environment, and Space	SH7_9 transportation, SH7_9 mobility, SH7_7 cities, PE6_7 artificial intelligence, PE6_7 intelligent systems, PE6_6 algorithms and complexity, SH7_10 spatial analysis	activity, household data
BME5	An extended method for the analysis of workplace mobility planning measures		11: Sustainable cities and communities	2: Climate, energy and mobility	SH7 Human Mobility, Environment, and Space	SH7_9 transportation, SH7_9 mobility, SH7_7 cities, SH3_6 group behaviour, SH7_6 climate change, SH7_6 societal impact	measure, mobility planning
BME6	Creation of a micromobility index for cities to support new mobility services		11: Sustainable cities and communities	2: Climate, energy and mobility	SH7 Human Mobility, Environment, and Space	SH7_9 transportation, SH7_9 mobility, SH7_7 cities, SH3_6 group behaviour, SH7_6 climate change, SH7_6 societal impact	index, micromobility

BME7	Analysis of travel behaviour and social networks to understand mobility patterns		11: Sustainable cities and communities	2: Climate, energy and mobility	SH7 Human Mobility, Environment, and Space	SH7_9 transportation, SH7_9 mobility, SH7_7 cities, PE6_7 artificial intelligence, PE6_7 intelligent systems, PE6_6 algorithms and complexity, SH7_10 spatial analysis	social network, mobility pattern
ENPC1	Microplastics in freshwater ecosystem	Protecting European Water	6: Clean water and sanitation	9 - Food, bioeconomy, natural resources, agriculture and environment	PE10 Earth System Science	PE10_17 Hydrology, hydrogeology, engineering and environmental geology, water and soil pollution	Plastic debris, microplastics, water, sediment, wastewater
ENPC2			4: Quality education, 7: Affordable and clean energy, 9: Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure	1 - Artificial Intelligence, 4 - Digitalization, 7 - Advanced material science and engineering	PE1 Mathematics	PE1_13 Probability, PE1_18 Numerical analysis, PE1_19 Scientific computing and data processing, PE1_21 Application of mathematics in sciences	Monte Carlo methods, analysis of PDEs, rare events, molecular dynamics

ENPC3	Narrative CV	Open science	4: Quality education; 5: Gender equality; 10: Reduced inequality; 9: Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure	3 - Social sciences and humanities; 4 - Digitalization; 8 - Culture, creativity and inclusive society	SH5 Cultures and Cultural Production; SH2 Institutions, Governance and Legal Systems; SH3 The Social World and Its Diversity; SH4 The Human Mind and Its Complexity; SH1 Individuals, Markets and Organisations;	SH1_11 Human resource management; operations management, marketing; SH2_1 Political systems, governance; SH3_1 Social structure, social mobility, social innovation; SH3_11 Social aspects of teaching and learning, curriculum studies, education and educational policies; SH3_12 Communication and information, networks, media; SH3_13 Digital social research; SH3_14 Social studies of science	Responsible Research Assessment, Narrative CV, scientometrics, bibliometrics, research integrity, open science, research impact, diversity and inclusion, DORA, Natural Language Processing, interviews
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ENPC4		Water in an era of change	6: Clean water and sanitation	11 - Natural Sciences	PE10 Earth System Science	PE10_9 Biogeochemistry, biogeochemical cycles, environmental chemistry; PE10_17 Hydrology, hydrogeology, engineering and environmental geology, water and soil pollution	Lake and river ecosystems; hydrodynamics; process-based modelling
ENPC5	Ecosystem performances assessment of Nature-based solutions for re-naturing urban environment	Green planet, protecting European waters, Sustainable Buildings, Cities and Communities	11: Sustainable cities and communities	10 - Climate, energy and mobility; 11 - Natural Sciences	PE10 Earth System Science	PE10_17 Hydrology, hydrogeology, engineering and environmental geology, water and soil pollution	Urban Hydrology, Nature-Based Solutions, Flooding, Urban Heat Island, green roof
FAU1	Development of an artificial intraurethral sphincter for therapy of urinary incontinence		SDG3 - Good health and well-being	4. Health	[LS7] Diagnostic Tools, Therapies and Public Health; [PE8] Products and Processes Engineering	[LS7_2] Medical technologies and tools; [LS7_12] Health care, including care for the ageing population; [PE8_7] Mechanical engineering	therapeutic approaches

FAU2	Mixed-Integer Non-Linear Optimisation: Algorithms and Applications		SDG 7 - Affordable and clean Energy; SDG 9 - Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure	1. Digital; 2. Climate, Energy Mobility; 9. Smart Industry and Space Technologies; 10. Natural Sciences; 11. Advanced Materials Science and Engineering	PE1: Mathematics	PE1_19 Control Theory and Optimization	Optimization
FAU3	Inventing a shared Science Diplomacy for Europe (InsciDE)		SDG 16 - Peace, justice and strong institutions	3. Social Sciences & Humanities	SH2: Institutions, Values, Beliefs and Behaviour	SH2_9 Global and transnational governance, international studies	International relations
FAU4	Designing and understanding the effects of gamified VR training on human-robot teaming		SDG 9 - Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure	1. Digital; 9. Smart Industry and Space Technologies	PE6: Computer Science and Informatics	PE6_8 Computer graphics, computer vision, multi media, computer games; PE6_9 Human computer interaction and interface, visualization and natural language processing	Human computer interaction
FAU5	Next Level Ecosphere for Intelligent Industrial Production		SDG 9 - Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure	5. Artificial Intelligence; 9. Smart Industry and Space Technologies	PE6: Computer Science and Informatics; PE8: Products and Processes Engineering	PE6_7 Artificial intelligence, intelligent systems, multi agent systems; PE8_10 Production technology, process engineering	Artificial intelligence; production technology

<p>ITU1</p>	<p>Treatment of water and wastewater using membrane technology</p>		<p>6 Clean Water and Sanitation</p>	<p>7 Food, Bio-economy, Natural Resources, Agriculture and Environment 10 Natural Sciences 11 Advanced Materials Science and Engineering</p>	<p>PE8 Products and Processes Engineering PE11 Materials Engineering</p>	<p>PE8_11 Environmental engineering, e.g. sustainable design, waste and water treatment, recycling, regeneration or recovery of compounds, carbon capture & storage PE11_9 Nanomaterials engineering, e.g. nanoparticles, nanoporous materials, 1D & 2D nanomaterials</p>	<p>Water and Wastewater Treatment/ Water and Wastewater Reuse/Membrane Technology/ Nanotechnology</p>
<p>ITU2</p>	<p>SME Cluster Growth</p>		<p>4 Quality Education 8 Decent Work and Economic Growth 9 Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure 12 Responsible Consumption and Production 17 Partnerships for the Goals</p>	<p>3 Social Sciences and Humanities 6 Connectivity 8 Culture, creativity and inclusive society</p>	<p>SH1 Individuals, Markets and Organisations</p>	<p>SH1_9 Industrial organisation; entrepreneurship; R&D and innovation SH1_10 Management; strategy; organisational behaviour</p>	<p>SME, HEI, cooperation</p>

ITU3	We'R'In		4 Quality Education 5 Gender Equality 10 Reduced Inequalities 16 Peace, Justice and Strong Institutions 17 Partnerships for the Goals	3 Social Sciences and Humanities 6 Connectivity 8 Culture, creativity and inclusive society	SH1 Individuals, Markets and Organisations SH3 The Social World and Its Diversity	SH1_9 Industrial organisation; entrepreneurship; R&D and innovation SH3_7 Kinship; diversity and identities, gender, interethnic relations	Entrepreneurship, inclusivity, women
ITU4	STEM Valorise		ALL	3 Social Sciences and Humanities 6 Connectivity 8 Culture, creativity and inclusive society	SH1 Individuals, Markets and Organisations	SH1_9 Industrial organisation; entrepreneurship; R&D and innovation SH1_10 Management; strategy; organisational behaviour	STEM, research, valorization
ITU5	Sustainable Real Estate Development: The Challenge of Affordable Housing		11 Sustainable Cities and Communities	3 Social Sciences and Humanities 8 Culture, creativity and inclusive society	SH7 Human Mobility, Environment, and Space	SH7_6 Environmental and climate change, societal impact and policy	Housing Markets, Real Estate Investment, Affordable Housing
ITU6	BEE GREEN: Enabling participatory activities through the use of mobile technologies to promote 'green' activities		11 Sustainable Cities and Communities 12 Responsible Consumption and Production	3 Social Sciences and Humanities 2 Climate, Energy and Mobility	SH7 Human Mobility, Environment, and Space	SH7_6 Environmental and climate change, societal impact and policy SH7_9 Energy, transportation and mobility	Smart City, Public Participation, Sustainability, Recycle/Reuse

<p>ITU7</p>	<p>Online Footprint - A serious game for reducing digital carbon emission</p>		<p>11 Sustainable Cities and Communities</p>	<p>3 Social Sciences and Humanities 2 Climate, Energy and Mobility</p>	<p>SH3 The Social World and Its Diversity SH7 Human Mobility, Environment, and Space</p>	<p>SH3_14 Social studies of science and technology SH7_6 Environmental and climate change, societal impact and policy</p>	<p>architectural survey, architectural excavation, survey, visualization, digital humanities, digital documentation, ancient architecture, medieval architecture, architectural education</p>
<p>ITU8</p>	<p>Analysing and Visualizing Walkability Experience</p>		<p>11 Sustainable Cities and Communities</p>	<p>3 Social Sciences and Humanities 8 Culture, creativity and inclusive society</p>	<p>SH7 Human Mobility, Environment, and Space</p>	<p>SH7_7 Cities; urban, regional and rural studies SH7_9 Energy, transportation and mobility</p>	<p>Walkability, decision-support systems, crowd- sourced data, visualization.</p>

<p>ITU9</p>	<p>Architect in Archaeological Field Studies</p>		<p>11 Sustainable Cities and Communities</p>	<p>3 Social Sciences and Humanities</p>	<p>SH5 Cultures and Cultural Production SH6 The Study of the Human Past</p>	<p>SH5_6 History of art and architecture, arts- based research SH5_8 Cultural studies, cultural identities and memories, cultural heritage SH6_2 Classical archaeology, history of archaeology, social archaeology SH6_6 Ancient history SH6_7 Medieval history</p>	
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<p>ITU10</p>	<p>National Center for High Performance Computing</p>		<p>4 Quality Education 11 Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure 17 Partnership for the Goals</p>	<p>1 Digital 5 Artificial Intelligence 6 Connectivity 9 Smart Industry and Space Technologies 10 Natural Sciences 11 Advanced Materials Science and Engineering</p>	<p>PE1 Mathematics PE4 Physical and Analytical Chemical Sciences PE6 Computer Science and Informatics PE11 Materials Engineering</p>	<p>PE1_19 Scientific computing and data processing PE4_13 Theoretical and computational chemistry PE6_2 Distributed systems, parallel computing, sensor networks, cyber-physical systems PE6_4 Theoretical computer science, formal methods, automata PE6_5 Security, privacy, cryptology, quantum cryptography PE6_12 Scientific computing, simulation and modelling tools</p>	<p>High Performance Computing, Cybersecurity, Cryptography, Computational Science, Materials Design</p>
<p>ITU11</p>	<p>Using multi-proxy data for paleoclimate and paleolimnology of the Anatolian lakes</p>		<p>13 Climate Action 14 Life Below Water</p>	<p>10 Natural Science</p>	<p>PE10 Earth System Science</p>	<p>PE10_6 Palaeoclimatology, palaeoecology PE10_12 Sedimentology, soil science, palaeontology, earth evolution</p>	<p>Anatolian lakes, paleoclimate, multi-proxy, sediment cores</p>

ITU12	Contribution to ship navigational safety and protection of marine environment in the Turkish Straits		14 Life below water 6 Clean water and sanitation 13 Climate action 4 Quality education	2 Climate, Energy and Mobility 3 Social Sciences and Humanities 9 Smart Industry and Space Technologies	PE8 Products and Processes Engineering SH7 Human Mobility, Environment, and Space	PE8_12 Naval/marine engineering SH7_9 Energy, transportation and mobility	Navigational Safety/Maritime Transportation/Risk Analysis/Turkish Straits, Safety
ITU13	Improving energy efficiency and resource utilization in data center facilities		7 Affordable and Clean Energy 9 Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure 11 Sustainable Cities and Communities 12 Responsible Consumption and Production 13 Climate Action	2 Climate, Energy and Mobility 9 Smart Industry and Space Technologies	PE7 Systems and Communication Engineering PE8 Products and Processes Engineering	PE7_3 Simulation engineering and modelling PE8_6 Energy processes engineering	Thermal environmental modeling and experiments, Grid-integrated data centers, sustainable communities, thermodynamic modeling and optimization
ITU14	Sustainable entrepreneurship in European Context: Mapping the business landscape and SDGs		ALL	8 Culture, creativity and inclusive society 3 Social sciences and humanities	SH1 Individuals, Markets and Organisations	SH1_9 Industrial organisation; entrepreneurship; R&D and innovation	

<p>ITU15</p>	<p>Digital Social Inclusion Aid Platform and Ecosystem Design- Building Collaborative and interactive social impact platform on theory and practice of Digital Social Inclusion of Vulnerable Groups in European Universities</p>	<p>ES: O4E</p>	<p>5 Gender Equality 10 Reduced Inequalities 17 Partnerships for the Goals</p>	<p>8 Culture, creativity and inclusive society 3 Social sciences and humanities</p>	<p>SH3 The Social World and Its Diversity</p>	<p>SH3_13 Digital social research</p>	
<p>ITU16</p>	<p>Nano Sized Surface Science</p>		<p>7 Affordable and clean energy 9 industry innovation and infrastructure</p>	<p>9 Smart Industry and Space Technologies 10 Natural Sciences 11 Advanced Materials Science and Engineering</p>	<p>PE3 Condensed Matter Physics PE11 Materials Engineering</p>	<p>PE3_6 Macroscopic quantum phenomena, e.g. superconductivity, superfluidity, quantum Hall effect PE11_9 Nanomaterials engineering, e.g. nanoparticles, nanoporous materials, 1D & 2D nanomaterials</p>	<p>2D materials, surface physics, nanotechnology, nanomaterials</p>

PSL1	Materials recycling, urban mines and secondary resource		SDG7, SDG11	Advanced material science and engineering 11, Climate, energy and mobility 2, Natural Sciences 10, Smart Industry and space technologies 9	PE4,PE5	PE4_1,PE4_2,PE4_5,PE5_10,PE5_6	WEEE, fly ashes, solution chemistry, in situ spectroscopy, Tungsten, Tantalum, Antimony
SNS1	Predicting extreme events by applying stochastic models to climate phenomena		13 Climate Action	2 Climate, energy and mobility, 10 Natural Sciences	PE1	PE1_10: ODE and dynamical systems; PE1_22 Application of mathematics in industry and society	Stochastic models Tipping points Extreme events
SNS2	Rotational and vibrational signatures of atmospheric pollutants		15 Life on Land	2 Climate, energy and mobility, 10 Natural Sciences	PE4	PE4_13: Theoretical and computational chemistry; PE4_2: Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques; PE10_1: Atmospheric chemistry, atmospheric composition, air pollution	Computational predictions Spectroscopy Atmospheric pollution

SNS3	Computational prediction of the spectroscopic properties of water contaminants	PROTECTING EUROPEAN WATERS	6 Clean water and Sanitation	2 Climate, energy and mobility, 10 Natural Sciences	PE4	PE4_13: Theoretical and computational chemistry; PE4_2: Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques; PE10_17: Hydrology, hydrogeology, engineering and environmental geology, water and soil pollution	Computational predictions Spectroscopy Water pollution
SNS4	Reducing the environmental impact of High Performance Computing		7 Affordable and clean energy	2 Climate, energy, mobility 10 Natural Science 6 Connectivity	PE6	PE6_2 parallel computing; PE6_12 Scientific computing, simulation and modelling tools	Numerical simulations Data science CO2 emission
SNS5	Preserving the starry sky visibility from artificial constellations		12 Responsible consumption and production	9 Smart Industry & Space technology 10 Natural Sciences 11 Advanced Materials Science and Engineering	PE9	PE8_1 Aerospace engineering; PE9_13 Astronomical instrumentation and data, e.g. telescopes, detectors, techniques, archives, analyses;	Constellation models Space sustainability Engineering
SNS6	Data sonification		3	4	LS7	LS7_14	

SSSA1	Sensing Sciences and Technologies	Organization of a conference	SDGs 3, 4, 8, 9, 11	1, 3, 4, 5	PE7, LS7, LS5	PE7_9 Man-machine interfaces; PE7_10 Robotics; PE7_11 Components and systems for applications (in e.g. medicine, biology, environment); LS5_7 Sensory systems, sensation and perception, including pain; SH4_5 Attention, perception, action, consciousness; LS7_14	Sensors, Senses
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SSSA2	APRIL - Applications of Personal Robotics for Interaction and Learning		3, 4, 8 , 9, 11	1, 3, 4, 5, 6,7	PE7 SH1 SH2 PE6	PE7_9 Man- machine- interfaces PE7_10 Robotics SH1_9 Competitiveness, innovation, research and development SH2_11 Social studies of science and technology PE6_3 Software engineering, operating systems, computer languages PE7_2 Electrical and electronic engineering: semiconductors, components, systems	economics and business, business and management, entrepreneurship engineering and technology, electrical engineering, electronic engineering, information engineering, electronic engineering, autonomous robots
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SSSA3	VASHARO - VARIABLE SHARED Autonomy ROBOT for collaborative bimanual grasping, handling and manipulation tasks		3, 8, 9, 11	1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7	PE7 SH1 SH2 PE6	PE7_9 Man- machine- interfaces PE7_10 Robotics SH1_9 Competitiveness, innovation, research and development SH2_11 Social studies of science and technology PE6_3 Software engineering, operating systems, computer languages PE7_2 Electrical and electronic engineering: semiconductors, components, systems	economics and business, business and management, entrepreneurship engineering and technology, electrical engineering, electronic engineering, information engineering, electronic engineering, autonomous robots
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SSSA4	UNDERTREES		4,11,15, 7	3, 8, 9	SH3 PE10 LS8	<p>SH3_1 Environment, resources and sustainability</p> <p>SH3_2 Environmental change and society</p> <p>SH3_4 Social and industrial ecology</p> <p>SH3_9 Spatial development and architecture, land use, regional planning</p> <p>SH3_12 Geo-information and spatial data analysis</p> <p>PE10_4 Terrestrial ecology, land cover change</p> <p>LS8_1 Ecology (theoretical and experimental; population, species and community level)</p>	<p>Ecosystem services, integrated sustainability assessment, carbon balance, greenhouse gas mitigation, resilience, land degradation, land management, policy development, stakeholder engagement</p>
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UPB1	ALAMEDA - Bridging the Early Diagnosis and Treatment Gap of Brain Diseases via Smart, Connected, Proactive and Evidence-based Technological Interventions		3. Good Health and Well-being	5. Artificial Intelligence	PE6 Computer Science and Informatics	PE6_7 Artificial intelligence, intelligent systems, multi agent systems	
UPB2	Enhancing and Improving Customer Experience and Services in Supermarkets via SMART Artificial Intelligence Powered Systems		7. Affordable and Clean Energy	5. Artificial Intelligence	PE6 Computer Science and Informatics	PE6_13 Bioinformatics, biocomputing, and DNA and molecular computation	
UPB3	AWEAR - A network for dynamic WEearable Applications with pRivacy constraints		2. Zero hunger	6. Connectivity	PE7 Systems and Communication Engineering	PE7_8 Networks (communication networks, sensor networks, networks of robots...)	mobile devices, wearables, privacy
UPB4	FARGO - Federated leARninG for human moBility		9. Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure	6. Connectivity	PE6 Computer Science and Informatics	PE6_11 Machine learning, statistical data processing and applications using signal processing (edge computing

UPB5	Skilled: Sustainable Skills for Local Developer (Skilled)		5. Gender equality	3. Social sciences and humanities	SH3 The Social World and Its Diversity	SH3_11 Social aspects of teaching and learning, curriculum studies, education and educational policies	smart communities
UPB6	Promoting social responsibility of students by embedding service learning within HEIs curricula (ENGAGE STUDENTS)		4. Quality Education	3. Social sciences and humanities	SH2 Institutions, Values, Beliefs and Behaviour	SH2_5 International relations, global and transnational governance	
UPB7	DECIP - Supporting the increase of the institutional research capacity of the University POLITEHNICA of Bucharest		17. Partnership for the Goals	1. Digitalization	PE6 Computer Science and Informatics	PE6_10 Web and information systems, data management systems, information retrieval and digital libraries, data fusion	digitalisation, CRIS
UPB8	Smaryd - Marketplace for technology transfer of R&I data, software and results		12. Responsible Consumption and Production	1. Digitalization	PE6 Computer Science and Informatics	PE6_10 Web and information systems, data management systems, information retrieval and digital libraries, data fusion	open data, digital objects

UPB9	cINnAMON - A non-intrusive home surveillance system for assisting elderly persons with frailty risk		3. Good Health and Well-being	4. Health	LS7 Diagnostic Tools, Therapies and Public Health	LS7_9 Public health and epidemiology	public health and epidemiology
UPB10	Sound of Vision		3. Good Health and Well-being	4. Health	LS7 Diagnostic Tools, Therapies and Public Health	LS7_14 Digital medicine, e-medicine, medical applications of artificial intelligence	medical engineering and technology, sound using digital tools
UPB11	Reinforcing Non-University Sector at the Tertiary Level in Engineering and Technology to Support Thailand Sustainable Smart Industry		9. Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure	9. Smart industry and space technologies	SH3 Environment, Space and Population	SH3_1 Social structure, social mobility, social innovation	social and industrial ecology
UPB12	Connecting Learning Factories for Promoting Manufacturing Education in South-East Europe		17. Partnership for the Goals	9. Smart industry and space technologies	SH3 Environment, Space and Population	SH3_14 Social studies of science and technology	population dynamics, aging, health and society
UPB13	SPERO: Space technologies in the management of major disasters and crises, manifested at local, national and regional level		15 Life on Land	9. Smart industry and space technologies	PE10 Earth System Science	PE10_21 Earth system modelling and interactions	very large data bases: archiving, handling and analysis, disaster management, satellite products, ESA hub

UPB14	Education 4.0: Living Labs for the Students of the Future (LLSF)		4. Quality Education	9. Smart industry and space technologies	SH4 The Human Mind and Its Complexity	SH4_7 Reasoning, decision-making; intelligence	education: systems and institutions, teaching and learning, digital twins, smart labs
UPB15	Holistic Approach for Valorization and Rehabilitation of the Metallurgical and Extractive Waste Deposits		13. Climate Action	11. Advanced material science and engineering	PE5 Synthetic Chemistry and Materials	PE5_8 Intelligent materials synthesis – self assembled materials	
UPB16	Surface coating and Microstructuring for compound functionalised biomaterials in dentistry		9. Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure	11. Advanced material science and engineering	PE4 Physical and Analytical Chemical Sciences	PE4_18 Environment chemistry	
UPB17	Nanochip - Multifunctional lab-on-a-chip microfluidic platform for the fabrication of nanoparticles		9. Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure	11. Advanced material science and engineering	PE3 Condensed Matter Physics	PE3_4 Electronic properties of materials, surfaces, interfaces, nanostructures	nano-materials
UPB18	Inclusive Responsible Research. Knowledge Mobilisation and University Social Responsibility		10. Reduced Inequalities	8. Culture, creativity and inclusive society	SH1 Individuals, Institutions and Markets	SH1_9 Industrial organisation; entrepreneurship; R&D and innovation	development, economic growth
UPB19	Team Class Coaching project		4. Quality Education	8. Culture, creativity and inclusive society	SH2 Institutions, Values, Beliefs and Behaviour	SH2_5 International relations, global and transnational governance	social policies, work and welfare

UPB20	High performance graphene-based aptasensors through versatile diazonium chemistry for detection of food contaminants		2. Zero hunger	7. Food, bioeconomy, natural resources, agriculture and environment	LS9 Applied life Sciences and Non-Medical Biotechnology	LS9_5 Food biotechnology and bioengineering	synthetic biology, chemical biology and new bio-engineering concepts
UPB21	Technology for obtaining an innovative antimicrobial, non-active medical dressing through the use of indigenous bioresources		13. Climate Action	7. Food, bioeconomy, natural resources, agriculture and environment	LS9 Applied life Sciences and Non-Medical Biotechnology	LS9_11 Biomass production and utilisation, biofuels	applied biotechnology (non-medical), bioreactors, applied microbiology
UPB22	SmartAgriHubs: Connecting the dots to unleash the innovation potential for digital transformation of the European agri-food sector		15. Life on Land	7. Food, bioeconomy, natural resources, agriculture and environment	LS9 Applied life Sciences and Non-Medical Biotechnology	LS9_5 Food biotechnology and bioengineering	agriculture related to animal husbandry, dairying, livestock raising, digital agriculture
UPB23	Smart Digital Solution for Local Green Energy Management		13. Climate Action	2. Climate, energy and mobility	PE8 Products and Processes Engineering	PR8_6 Energy systems (production, distribution, application)	
UPB24	rEsilient and seLf-healed EleCTRICAL pOwer Nanogrid		12. Responsible Consumption and Production	2. Climate, energy and mobility	PE8 Products and Processes Engineering	PR8_4 Computational engineering	

UPB25	Data2Water - Excellence in Smart Data and Services for Supporting Water Management	protecting European waters	13. Climate Action	2. Climate, energy and mobility	PE10 Earth System Science	PE10_17 Hydrology, hydrogeology, engineering and environmental geology, water and soil pollution	hydrology
UPM1	Digitalization to learn Multiple Sclerosis evolution (Long Term Gait Monitoring)		SDG3	4. Health 5. Artificial Intelligence	LS7 Prevention, Diagnosis and Treatment of Human Diseases	LS7_2 Medical technologies and tools (including genetic tools and biomarkers) for prevention, diagnosis, monitoring and treatment of diseases LS7_14 Digital medicine, e-medicine, medical applications of artificial intelligence	Multiple Sclerosis; Digitalization; Machine learning; IoT
UPM2	Quantum Computing in cooperation with Deep Learning for Industrial Quality		SDG9	1. Digital 5. Artificial intelligence 9. Smart Industry & Space Technologies	PE6 Computer Science and Informatics PE8 Products and Processes Engineering	PE6_14 Quantum computing (formal methods, algorithms and other computer science aspects) PE8_9 Production technology, process engineering	DSS; AI; QC; Industrial Quality; Complex processes

<p>UPM3</p>	<p>Improving hydrology understanding through data-driven approaches</p>		<p>OD6</p>	<p>2. Climate, Energy & Mobility 5. Artificial Intelligence</p>	<p>PE10: Earth System Science PE6: Computer Science and Informatics</p>	<p>PE10_17: Hydrology, hydrogeology, engineering and environmental geology, water and soil pollution PE10_3: Climatology and climate change PE1_19: Scientific computing and data processing PE6_7: Artificial intelligence, intelligent systems, natural language processing</p>	<p>Hydrology, physical models, data-driven models, climate change</p>
<p>UPM4</p>	<p>Wearable devices for the prevention, diagnosis and treatment of diseases.</p>		<p>OD4 Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages, cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable 3. Good health and well being</p>	<p>4. Health 5. Artificial Intelligence</p>	<p>LS7 Prevention, Diagnosis and Treatment of Human Diseases</p>	<p>LS7_2 Medical technologies and tools (including genetic tools and biomarkers) for prevention, diagnosis, monitoring and treatment of diseases LS7_14 Digital medicine, e-medicine, medical applications of artificial intelligence</p>	<p>wearable, electronics, sensors, edge computing, wireless</p>

<p>UPM5</p>	<p>Biopolymeric nanomaterials based transition-metal dichalcogenide nanostructures (TMDCs)</p>		<p>Biobased and Biodegradable Materials SD13 Climate Action</p>	<p>10. Natural Sciences 11. Advanced Materials Science and Engineering</p>	<p>PE11 Materials Engineering PE5 Synthetic Chemistry and Materials</p>	<p>PE11_1 Engineering of biomaterials, biomimetic, bioinspired and bio-enabled materials PE11_9 Nanomaterials engineering, e.g. nanoparticles, nanoporous materials, 1D & 2D nanomaterials PE5_1 Structural properties of materials</p>	<p>Morphology, Crystallization behaviour, Mechanical properties, Biodegradation</p>
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